

Evaluation of Road Safety Infrastructure and Identification of Accident-Prone Zones on an Indian National Highway

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Abstract: India records the highest number of road traffic fatalities globally, with national highways contributing a disproportionate share of severe and fatal crashes. Despite continued highway expansion, persistent deficiencies in road safety design and maintenance remain critical risk factors. This study evaluates road safety infrastructure and identifies accident-prone zones along a 140.3 km stretch of National Highway-48 (NH-48) between Pune and Satara, Maharashtra.

A corridor-level road safety audit was conducted using a four-dimensional framework encompassing engineering, enforcement, emergency care, and road user engagement. Primary data were obtained through systematic daytime and night-time field surveys and chainage-wise mapping of safety deficiencies, supported by secondary data from police records and national standards.

The analysis identified 29 safety-critical deficiencies across 14 categories, with major issues including absent or improperly terminated crash barriers, untreated median gaps, faded pavement markings, potholes, inadequate pedestrian facilities, and poor drainage. Spatial clustering revealed multiple high-risk zones, highlighting the dominant role of infrastructure-induced risks and the need for system-based safety interventions on Indian highways.

Keywords: Road safety audit, accident-prone zones, national highways, infrastructure safety, India, NH-48

1. Introduction

Road traffic injuries represent a critical public health and infrastructure challenge in India. According to national statistics, although national highways constitute a small fraction of the total road network, they account for more than one-third of road fatalities. Rapid motorization, mixed traffic conditions, and inconsistent safety design exacerbate crash risk, particularly on high-speed corridors.

NH-48 is one of India's most important arterial highways, carrying substantial passenger and freight traffic. The Pune–

Satara section has experienced rapid urbanization, increased traffic volumes, and frequent infrastructure modifications, making it particularly vulnerable to safety failures. Traditional crash analysis in India often attributes accidents primarily to human error, overlooking the systemic influence of road design and environment.

This study aims to bridge this gap by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of road safety infrastructure and identifying accident-prone zones using a structured, evidence-based audit framework.

2. Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this research are to:

1. Identify safety-critical infrastructure deficiencies along the NH-48 Pune–Satara corridor.
2. Quantify and spatially map accident-prone and high-risk locations.
3. Analyze the relationship between infrastructure deficiencies and crash vulnerability.
4. Evaluate compliance of existing infrastructure with Indian Road Congress (IRC) standards.
5. Propose data-driven recommendations to enhance corridor-level road safety.

3. Literature Review

Previous studies have established that road safety outcomes are strongly influenced by infrastructure quality, geometric consistency, and roadside protection. Research on rural and national highways in India highlights the prevalence of black spots caused by inadequate signage, unsafe median openings, and lack of pedestrian facilities.

International studies emphasize that road safety audits conducted before and after highway construction significantly reduce crash severity. However, in developing countries, audits are often reactive and fragmented. Indian studies further reveal that official crash records disproportionately assign blame to drivers, limiting the identification of infrastructure-induced risks.

This study builds upon existing literature by adopting a **corridor-level, infrastructure-centric approach**, integrating frequency analysis, spatial assessment, and standards-based evaluation.

4. Study Area Description

The study corridor comprises a 140.3 km stretch of NH-48 connecting Pune and Satara in Maharashtra. The highway predominantly consists of six lanes with a design speed of 80 km/h, interspersed with toll plazas, bridges, median openings, and service roads. The corridor passes through rural, semi-urban, and peri-urban zones, resulting in heterogeneous traffic composition and pedestrian interaction.

5. Methodology

5.1 Overall Framework

The study employed a **four-step crash vulnerability audit methodology**:

1. Data triangulation
2. On-site road safety audit
3. Identification and classification of risk factors
4. Development of safety recommendations

The methodology is aligned with international road safety audit practices and adapted to Indian traffic conditions.

6. Data Collection

6.1 Primary Data Collection

6.1.1 Road Safety Audit and Field Surveys

A comprehensive road safety audit was conducted along the entire corridor through:

- Daytime and night-time inspections
- Videographic and photographic documentation
- Chainage-based logging of deficiencies

Each safety issue was geo-referenced and categorized under predefined infrastructure elements.

6.1.2 Classification of Safety Factors

Observed elements were classified into:

- **Critical factors**, directly influencing crash occurrence or severity
- **Non-critical factors**, supporting navigational and operational efficiency

This study focuses primarily on critical factors.

Table 1: Condition Status of Safety-Critical Road Infrastructure on NH 48

Sr. no.	Issue	Factor	Frequency	Unit
1	Issues related to crash barrier	Absent Crash Barrier	233	km
		Damaged Crash Barrier	22	Spots
		Gap in Crash Barrier	79	Spots
		Inappropriate Termination of Crash Barrier	165	Spots
		Inappropriate Height of Crash Barrier	4	km
		Inappropriate Placement of Crash Barrier	16	Spots
2	Roadside hazard/obstruction	Hard Structures	153	Spots
		Exposed Trees	59	Spots
3	Vision Obstruction	Signage covered by vegetation	5	Spots
4	Issues related to road signage	Absence of Sign Board	117	Spots
		Damaged Signage	5	Spots
5	Pavement marking	Absence or Discontinuous Pavement Marking	69	km
		Dashed line	58	Spots

		before entry/exit faded		
		Rumble strips - faded	15	Spots
6	Construction zone	Improper Construction Zone	4	Spots
7	Pavement	Potholes	348	Spots
		Pooling of water due to poor drainage	31	Spots
8	Safety issues at the median gap	Untreated Gap in Median	38	Spots
		Broken/Discontinuous Median gap	16	Spots
9	Safety issues related to pedestrian infrastructure	Pedestrian Crossing Absent/Faded	24	Spots
		Absent or Broken Pedestrian Guard Rail	13	Spots
		Inappropriate location of the pedestrian crosswalk	6	Spots
10	Transportation system	Absence of Designated Bus Stop	4	Spots
11	Unauthorized activities	Roadside Encroachment	17	Spots
		Unauthorized Roadside Parking (Day)	47	Spots
		Unauthorized Roadside Parking (Night)	73	Spots
12	Geometric inconsistency	Improper Access to Highway	28	Spots
		Sudden Lane drop	8	Spots
		Absent/Inadequate shoulder	74	km
13	Safety issues related to intersections	Untreated Intersections	4	Spots
14	Nighttime safety issues	Inadequate/Absent Illumination	4	Spots
		Absent Road Delineation	82	Spots
		Absent / Inadequate glare block	30	Spots

6.2 Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data sources included:

- Police accident records
- Concessionaire maintenance reports
- National and state road safety publications

Additionally, infrastructure elements were evaluated against IRC standards such as IRC:35 (Road Markings), IRC:67 (Road Signs), IRC:119 (Traffic safety barriers), IRC:SP 99 (Specifications and standards for Expressways), IRC:SP 87 (Specifications & Standards for 6-Laning of Highways through Public-Private Partnership), IRC:79 (Practice for Road Delineators) and IRC:82 (Maintenance of Bituminous Road Surfaces).

7. Data Analysis

7.1 Frequency Analysis of Safety Deficiencies

A frequency-based analysis was conducted to quantify infrastructure deficiencies. Linear features were measured in kilometers, while point hazards were recorded as discrete locations. A total of 29 safety-critical factors were identified under 14 categories.

The most frequently observed deficiencies included:

- Absence of crash barriers along extensive corridor lengths
- Improper termination and gaps in existing crash barriers
- High incidence of potholes and surface distress
- Absence or fading of pavement markings
- Untreated and unauthorized median openings
- Inadequate pedestrian crossings and guardrails

7.2 Spatial Analysis and Identification of Accident-Prone Zones

Spatial clustering of deficiencies was used to identify accident-prone zones. Locations exhibiting multiple overlapping risk factors—such as median gaps combined with poor signage and pedestrian activity—were classified as high-risk zones even in cases of underreported crash data.

7.3 Risk Severity Assessment

Each safety issue was evaluated based on:

- Likelihood of crash occurrence
- Potential severity of injury or fatality
- Exposure to traffic volume and vulnerable road users

This qualitative risk assessment enabled prioritization of countermeasures based on potential safety impact.

8. Results and Discussion

The analysis indicates that infrastructure-related deficiencies play a dominant role in crash vulnerability along the NH-48 corridor. The widespread absence of continuous crash barriers and the presence of untreated median openings significantly increase the likelihood of fatal run-off-road and head-on collisions.

Pedestrian safety infrastructure was found to be severely inadequate, particularly in built-up areas, leading to unsafe crossing behavior. Poor drainage and pavement deterioration further exacerbate crash risk, especially during monsoon conditions.

These findings challenge the conventional narrative of human error as the primary crash cause and emphasize the systemic role of road design and maintenance.

9. Recommendations

Based on the analysis, the study recommends:

- Corridor-wide installation and continuity of crash barriers
- Closure of unauthorized median openings and proper treatment of necessary gaps
- Restoration of pavement markings and signage as per IRC standards
- Provision of safe pedestrian crossings with guardrails and retro-reflective features
- Regular, independent road safety audits and proactive asset management

10. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that systematic deficiencies in road safety infrastructure significantly contribute to crash risk and severity on Indian national highways. Through detailed data collection and analysis, the research highlights the need for a shift from reactive, site-specific interventions to proactive, corridor-level safety planning.

The findings provide actionable insights for highway authorities and policymakers aiming to achieve safer highways and move toward the goal of zero fatalities. The methodology and results presented in this study can serve as a replicable framework for evaluating road safety on similar high-speed corridors across India.

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